

Extra Linguistic Issues In Cross-Cultural Attitude Rituals And Traditions

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Abstract: They need for cross-cultural communication skills arises whenever people from different languages and cultures come into contact. With increased tourism, international business, student studying overseas and increasing awareness of indigenous minority cultures there is concern to foster better communications among different cultural groups.

Keywords:Culture,Communication, Languages, Community,

Culture is a way of thinking and living whereby one picks up a set of attitudes, values, norms and beliefs that are taught and reinforced by other members in the group. This set of basic assumptions and solutions to the problems of the world is a shared system that is passed on from generation to generation to ensure survival. A culture consists of unwritten and written principles and laws that guide how an individual interacts with the outside world. Members of a culture can be identified by the fact that they share some similarity. They may be united by religion, by geography, by race or ethnicity.

Our cultural understanding of the world and everything in it ultimately affects our style of communication as we start picking up ways of one's culture at around the same time we start learning to communicate. Culture influences the words we

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other side”. There are various requirements for successful interaction in a multicultural environment; the importance of self-awareness and attitude is often underestimated.[2]

Extra-linguistic and paralinguistic issues Linguistic issues An individual’s attitude shapes their habits and behavior. And group behavior ultimately influences an organization’s culture.

So, to improve your culture, you must first focus on changing people’s attitudes.

Rituals lie in the center of the core belief systems of the people who practice them.

Rituals bring about a sense of group identity, and therefore strengthen and build community Habit is ???

A routine of behavior that is repeated regularly and tends to occur subconsciously

Fixed way of thinking, willing, or feeling acquired through previous repetition of a mental experience Defined from the standpoint of psychology

The most interesting customs around the world.[3]

[1]<https://www.communicationtheory.org/cross-cultural-communication/>

[https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-attitude-cross-cultural-](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-attitude-cross-cultural-communication-tilman-rieger)

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reference

[2][https:// azkurs.org/ subj ect--cultural- comm unicati on -topic-extra-lin gui sti c- issues.html](https://azkurs.org/subject--cultural-communication-topic-extra-linguistic-issues.html)

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[3]<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-attitude-cross-cultural-communication-tilman-rieger>